

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Building Bridges, Not Just Events: Lessons in Diversity, Cross-fertilisation, and Impact for Science Comes to Town

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Journal of Science Communication (JCOM): JCOM is a peer-reviewed journal for science communication, covering topics such as public engagement with STEM, and challenges arising in science communication. According to the author's guidelines, the manuscript should be 5,000 to 8,000 words, with an abstract of 100-150 words (here: 141). The APA citation style is used for referencing. For the sake of completeness of this research thesis, the manuscript is longer than 8,000 words (AI disclaimer, References and Appendices are around 3000 words together, leaving around 9000 words for the main body of work).

Keywords: European City of Science, cross-fertilisation, community-building, stakeholder diversity.

Abstract

Public engagement is increasingly essential in science communication, particularly within large-scale initiatives such as the European City of Science (ECS) and Culture (ECoC). This study explores how stakeholder diversity shapes interdisciplinary collaboration and community-building, intending to inform the upcoming Science Comes to Town (SCTT) initiative. Using a mixed methods approach, three ECS case studies (Manchester 2016, Leiden 2022, Katowice 2024) and 12 semi-structured interviews with ECS and ECoC stakeholders were conducted. Quantitative analysis of stakeholder composition and thematic focus was combined with qualitative insights on collaboration models and planning strategies of diversity. Results show that higher stakeholder diversity fosters more bottom-up programming, cross-sector collaboration, and co-ownership. Cities operating in more hierarchical governance contexts tended towards top-down, academic-led models of engagement. This research offers practical guidance for SCTT, highlighting that locally driven stakeholder diversity can support more inclusive public engagement.

1. Introduction

As science and society become increasingly interconnected, public engagement with research is necessary (Stilgoe et al., 2014). Today's scientific challenges demand dialogue, not just dissemination (Irwin, 2015). According to the latest Eurobarometer findings, citizens across Europe want science to be more open, relevant, and responsive to their experiences. While 83% of Europeans view science and technology positively, many call for more equitable access to their benefits and greater involvement of non-scientists in research (European Commission, 2025). These numbers highlight the need for inclusive strategies that reflect diverse values and foster long-term collaboration between researchers and communities.

Over recent decades, science communication has evolved from one-way dissemination models towards more participatory and two-way communication frameworks. As emphasised by Bucchi & Trench (2021), science communication is shifting from fixed frameworks to a more dynamic understanding, incorporating new formats to facilitate conversations between science and society. The American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS) Theory of Change for Public Engagement with Science (AAAS, 2016) highlights these shifts by outlining a model where scientists, publics, and practitioners engage in different interaction types. These evolving models provide the foundation for a more participatory science communication.

Two key concepts increasingly shaping this shift are cross-fertilisation and community-building. Cross-fertilisation is a process where different disciplines, knowledge systems, and stakeholders share and integrate their expertise, often leading to novel insights and breakthroughs (CORDIS, 2014). Here, stakeholder

theory provides a useful lens, recognising that each actor brings distinct interests, which should all be considered to achieve greater success and sustainability (Freeman et al., 2020). Community-building focuses on bringing people together through shared actions and interests, creating a sense of connection and belonging among everyone involved (van den Bergh, 2022). Both have emerged as essential pillars in European initiatives like the European Cities of Science (ECS) and European Capitals of Culture (ECoC), which offer models for embedding science and culture in everyday life. For example, during Leiden's ECS year in 2022, the "Knowledge Throughout the Neighbourhoods" programme invited residents to create their own science activities. These events saw up to 23,500 participants, with 134 local stakeholders co-creating more than 200 activities (Leiden2022-ECS-ESOF, 2023, pp.4-5). Despite such successes, challenges remain, particularly in meaningfully integrating stakeholder diversity and cultural contexts into science communication efforts.

Indeed, evaluations of large-scale citizen science projects have repeatedly found that participants tend to be from already well-connected, higher socioeconomic backgrounds, leading to skewed representation (Allf et al., 2022). One promising approach to address these challenges is participatory, curiosity-driven engagement (Stilgoe et al., 2014). This includes events and initiatives that not only communicate scientific knowledge but also actively involve diverse communities in shaping how science is understood and applied. Cross-fertilisation is especially effective when it incorporates culturally diverse perspectives, often leading to novel insights and more inclusive forms of collaboration (González-Piñero et al., 2021). Yet, as Strzelecki et al. (2024) argue, the integration of cultural values and diverging backgrounds into these processes is still underdeveloped, and a better understanding of how cultural context shapes engagement remains limited.

Lessons from projects like the Cities and Science Communication (CASC) initiative, ECS, and ECoC underscore the importance of flexible, interdisciplinary strategies tailored to local needs. CASC was a European Commission project run from 2009 to 2011, described as "set out to explore existing methods and approaches to building a scientific culture, including their impact on specific target groups and the potential for transferability between countries and cultures" (CORDIS, 2017). ECS, coordinated by EuroScience and the European Commission, designates a city per year as a hub for science engagement. It aims to encourage public participation, foster accessibility, and spark curiosity across diverse audiences (European Union, 2023). Meanwhile, ECoC celebrates culture in multiple European cities annually, often incorporating scientific themes in the arts to highlight the intersection between science, culture, and society. Together, these initiatives create opportunities to study cross-fertilisation and community-building, as they actively aim to engage citizens, artists, scientists, and many other stakeholders in shaping these experiences. Still, significant barriers persist, particularly linguistic and professional fragmentation, and concerns over inclusivity (Davies et al., 2021).

The Science Comes to Town 2026 (SCTT26) project builds on these findings. Designed as a year-long initiative in Brest, Split, and Kiel, it aims to integrate science into everyday urban life through participatory, community-based activities. Aligned with the European Commission's vision for citizen engagement and youth inspiration (European Commission, 2024), SCTT26 foregrounds collaboration between researchers, policymakers, and citizens, with a focus on cultural inclusivity and long-term impact.

Despite these promising frameworks, a critical knowledge gap remains: how does stakeholder diversity influence the effectiveness of interdisciplinary collaboration and community-building in science communication? While the value of diversity is often acknowledged, there is limited comparative research on how cultural and contextual differences shape outcomes across European cities. Existing research shows that language, tradition, social norms, and local history influence how communities perceive and engage with science (Li, 2014; Marsh et al., 2023; Valdez-Ward et al., 2024). Addressing this complexity can strengthen trust, participation, and long-term impact.

This study addresses that gap by examining how inclusive cross-fertilisation strategies supported community-building in three ECS cities: Manchester (2016), Leiden (2022), and Katowice (2024). Each adopted a distinct model shaped by its political, historical, and geographical context. Manchester's one-week programme emphasised short-term public engagement in a pre-Brexit, pre-pandemic UK. Six years later, Leiden pioneered a year-long ECS format embedding science into everyday life. More recently, Katowice, a city of a newer EU member state, adopted this model in a Central European context.

In parallel, this research draws on lessons from the European Capitals of Culture (ECoC), an initiative active since 1985, known for its efforts in cultural inclusivity, city-wide participation, and cross-sectoral collaboration (Garcia & Cox, 2013). ECoC and ECS share similar ambitions (fostering European identity, interdisciplinary engagement, and civic ownership), making ECoC a valuable comparative model.

By comparing these cases, this study investigates how stakeholder diversity influenced interdisciplinary collaboration, community-building, and long-term engagement in ECS and ECoC initiatives. It aims to identify contrasts, commonalities, and critical success factors that can inform the development of SCTT26.

The central research question guiding this study is: **What can SCTT26 learn from how stakeholder diversity influenced the effectiveness of interdisciplinary collaboration and community-building during previous ECS and ECoC?**

This question will be addressed through the following subquestions:

- How did stakeholder diversity shape cross-fertilisation approaches in previous ECS and ECoC?
- To what extent was diversity strategically planned in these events, and how did this impact the effectiveness of community-building efforts?
- What challenges emerged in integrating different cultural backgrounds and sectors into community-building efforts through cross-fertilisation strategies?
- How did stakeholder diversity enhance the sustainability and perceived impact of community-building initiatives in ECS and ECoC, both for stakeholders and participants?
- What lessons and strategies can SCTT26 adopt to enhance inclusivity and cross-fertilisation in its community-building efforts?

This study examines how inclusive cross-fertilisation practices support community-building in science communication. Through comparative analysis and stakeholder interviews, it identifies how stakeholder diversity shapes engagement outcomes. Findings reveal that higher stakeholder diversity supports more bottom-up programming, cross-sector collaboration, and shared ownership, while governance context influences the degree of inclusivity and engagement models.

2. Methods

a. Target population

A wide range of stakeholders contributed to the success of ECS initiatives by bringing diverse expertise, perspectives, and functions. Table 1 below summarises the key stakeholder groups involved, their primary roles in supporting cross-fertilisation and community-building, and relevant supporting literature.

Table 1. Key stakeholders and their roles in ECS initiatives.

Stakeholder group	Role/contribution	References
Organisers and Project managers	Central role in creating environments that foster knowledge exchange and innovation by bridging diverse sectors, such as academia, industry, and the public.	Enger & Gulbrandsen (2020)
Creative directors	Contribute perspectives on how creative approaches enhance engagement and collaboration.	Schäfer & Kieslinger (2016)
Museum staff	Help tailor content for diverse audiences and promote lifelong learning.	Falk & Dierking (2018)
Municipal representatives	Foster collaboration between science and policy.	Abdullah & Roig (2021)
Researchers and science communicators	Bridge the gap between complex science and public understanding.	Besley et al. (2018)
Local businesses	Provide logistical and financial support critical for event success.	Edmiston (2007)

Including this diverse range of voices aligns with stakeholder engagement theories, emphasising inclusive dialogue to co-create solutions that meet the needs of all parties (Bryson, 2004). Moreover, as past studies on public engagement initiatives have shown (Besley et al., 2016; Canfield et al., 2022), capturing viewpoints across stakeholder groups enhances the validity and applicability of findings to real-world contexts.

b. Case Studies on European Cities of Science

Manchester (ECS16), Leiden (ECS22), and Katowice (ECS24) served as the main case studies for this study as they represented diverse contexts and strategies, offering a broad spectrum of approaches to study (Table 2).

Table 2. Overview of the Manchester (2016), Leiden (2022), and Katowice (2024) ECS editions used as case studies, including program length, key features, and references.

City	ECS Edition	Program Length	Key Features	References
Manchester (United Kingdom)	2016	Focused on a one-week conference with satellite events in the city	Industrial heritage; centre for scientific and technological breakthroughs. Pre-Brexit and pre-pandemic edition	The University of Manchester (2024); ESOF 2016 (2016)
Leiden (Netherlands)	2022	Year-round	Historic university city; academic excellence and innovation hub.	Leiden2022 (2022)
Katowice (Poland)	2024	Year-round	First year-round edition. First Central European ECS; newer EU member state.	Strzelecki et al. (2024)

In studying these ECSs, the analysis focused on identifying stakeholder diversity, collaboration patterns, thematic areas of activity, and the spatial distribution of events across neighbourhoods. Names of stakeholders (especially directors of events) were also collected during this process to collect potential contacts for the upcoming interviews.

c. Stakeholder diversity and interdisciplinary collaboration

i) Stakeholder mapping

To assess stakeholder diversity for each city, stakeholder mapping was conducted using the official ECS websites, reports, and policy documents (document analysis). This method involved identifying, categorising, and analysing stakeholders based on their affiliations at the time of the respective ECS. An inductive approach was used to define stakeholder categories, ensuring that the classification reflected the diversity of actors involved in each ECS edition. Thirteen categories were identified, and the same categories were used for the three studied ECS editions. A list of the stakeholder categories can be found in Appendix 1. This approach aligns with methods of stakeholder analysis that highlight the diversity of actors and the quality of their participation (Reed et al, 2018).

Stakeholders were classified as internal (organisers, funders, steering groups) or external (speakers, collaborators, activity partners). This way, stakeholder diversity was assessed in terms of sector, both internally and externally. All stakeholder data used were publicly available through official ECS reports and websites. No personally identifiable information was collected or analysed.

A Fisher's exact test was conducted to examine the association between stakeholder categories and their internal or external status. This test was selected due to the presence of categories with low counts ($n < 5$), which ruled out the use of chi-square tests. Analysis of residuals allowed to determine significant differences between internal and external representation in each stakeholder category. Additionally, due to non-normality and unequal variances, a Poisson regression was used to assess differences across categories after filtering out zero-count groups. Post-hoc comparisons were conducted using Tukey's test. Fisher's exact test and the Poisson regression model with their corresponding assumptions were performed in RStudio (RStudio version 4.4.1).

ii) Collaboration network analysis

Furthermore, stakeholder mapping provided insights into interdisciplinary collaboration. All individual events that included at least two different types of stakeholders were listed, as well as their corresponding stakeholder categories. From these, co-occurrence matrices were created from which the networks were

built. The networks were created using Gephi (Version 0.10.0). This approach helped to visualise patterns of collaborations, highlight underrepresented groups, and identify which stakeholder categories were central to cross-sector collaborations. This approach aligns with methodologies in stakeholder analysis within public engagement contexts, where visualising collaborations appears as a way to understand influence and gaps in representation (Syed et al., 2024).

iii) Shannon's diversity index

Shannon's diversity index was used to calculate stakeholder diversity for both internal and external stakeholders. Shannon's diversity index is commonly used in environmental sciences to characterise an ecosystem's diversity (Turner et al., 2001; Ramezani et al., 2010). The index takes into account the variety and abundance of species within an environment (Shannon, 1948). As the main assumption for using this formula is that all species are present in the environment and can be randomly sampled, we determined the possibility of using this formula to determine stakeholder diversity within each studied ECS. Moreover, Shannon's index has been adapted in previous studies to measure diversity in organisational settings (Zetina-Rejón et al., 2020).

Thus, stakeholder diversity was evaluated using the following formula:

$H = - \sum [(p_i) \times \ln(p_i)]$, with p_i the proportion of individuals in the i^{th} group relative to the total number of individuals across all groups.

Furthermore, evenness (E) was calculated for a more detailed result, using the following formula:

$E = \frac{H}{i}$, with i the number of stakeholder categories (in this case, 13).

d. Location analysis

Using the official ECS websites and their programmes, event zip codes were collected and then converted into geographic coordinates using the Google Maps API. The locations were then visualised as heat maps in Kepler.gl to show the spatial distribution of activities for each ECS edition.

To assess socioeconomic equity, heat maps were overlaid with income distribution maps of their respective cities. Income distribution maps were obtained for Manchester, Leiden, and Katowice, respectively, on: Plumplot (2020), Kansenskaart (2020), and Pifczyk (2024). Prior research suggests that diversity among organisers and stakeholders can effectively tailor events to broader communities by localising events in underserved areas (Glow et al., 2021; Hood et al., 2023).

Icons marking main university campuses were added to evaluate whether activities clustered around academic institutions, possibly indicating an imbalance in accessibility. Locations of main university campuses were obtained via Google Maps.

As England, the Netherlands and Poland all have different currencies, the legends of net income maps from Manchester and Katowice were converted into euros, using the average exchange rate respectively for ECS16 and ECS24 (sourced from exchange-rates.com).

e. Content analysis of activities

A content analysis of activities happening in neighbourhoods was conducted to analyse the amount and distribution of activities that were dedicated to inclusivity and community themes. The themes were coded inductively, resulting in seven themes: History, Culture, Age, Gender, Accessibility, Language, and Local People. Codes, described in Appendix 2. The codebook for this content analysis was tested with a second coder, who coded 10% of the data for each city. The selection of 10% of the data was random, using a random number generator. An intercoder reliability of 98.4% was obtained. History, Language, and Local People were chosen as codes as they can be considered to represent a familiar narrative to local audiences attending these events. Indeed, linking activities to the city's or country's heritage can create a familiar starting point for an audience, enhancing the perceived relevance (Longnecker, 2023). Age, Gender, Accessibility and Culture were added as codes as they are commonly recognised dimensions of social inclusion and diversity. These categories reflect efforts to engage traditionally underrepresented or marginalised groups, ensuring broader accessibility and representation in public engagement initiatives (Canfield et al., 2020). By coding for these themes, the analysis aimed to capture both culturally resonant content and structural inclusivity efforts, providing a more comprehensive understanding of how ECS activities addressed community relevance and inclusivity in their programming.

A Fisher's exact test on count data was used to compare the distribution of activity themes across the three ECS editions to assess whether categorical variables (themes and cities) were independent. Additionally, separate Fisher's exact tests were conducted per theme to identify which themes contributed most to the overall differences. The Fisher's exact test was performed in RStudio (RStudio version 4.4.1).

f. European Capitals of Culture

In addition to European Cities of Science, European Capitals of Culture were deemed to be an interesting comparison point in terms of stakeholder diversity and interdisciplinary/cross-border collaboration. Case studies were not conducted for these ECoC, but stakeholders were interviewed. Their perspectives offered

comparative insights that complement the ECS case studies and inform recommendations for SCTT26. Esch-sur-Alzette (2022) was selected due to its geographical context as well as its multiculturalism and multilingualism (Stogianni et al., 2021), offering useful insights for the future of SCTT26.

g. Interviews

Following these case studies, semi-structured interviews were conducted with 12 stakeholders from the selected ECS and ECoC to explore in-depth perspectives of cross-fertilisation and community-building. The main benefit of semi-structured interviews is that they allow the interviewer to explore relevant ideas that arise from the interviewee during the interview process (Croucher & Cronn-Mills, 2024). Various profiles of stakeholders (n=12) were interviewed to gain an overview of multiple points of view, and later incorporate their ideas to meet everyone's needs (Canfield et al., 2022; Enger & Gulbrandsen, 2020). The profiles, with their respective pseudonyms and ECS/ECoC cities, are detailed in Table 3. Interviewees were selected via stakeholder mapping and snowball sampling. Initial contacts were ECS/ECoC directors, who then recommended further participants using a guided question in the interview. Interviews lasted between 28 minutes and 1 hour and 24 minutes, with an average duration of 38 minutes.

Although ECoC was not a formal case study, its stakeholders were included due to the initiative's relevance in fostering inclusive, large-scale public engagement (Garcia & Cox, 2013).

Table 3. Pseudonymised interviewees, with their respective roles and city affiliations. Roles were obtained from the first question of each interview. City affiliations correspond to the European City of Science (ECS) or European Capital of Culture (ECoC) edition with which the interviewee was involved.

Interviewee pseudonyms	Coded role(s)	ECS/ECoC city
S1	Director	Leiden
S2	Director, Steering group member, Bid leader	Leiden
S3	Project manager/coordinator	Leiden
S4	Project manager/coordinator	Leiden
S5	Director	Katowice
S6	Director	Esch
S7	Project manager/coordinator	Esch
S8	Project manager/coordinator	Leiden
S9	Steering group member	Manchester
S10	Director	Katowice
S11	Project manager/coordinator	Katowice
S12	Director	Katowice

To avoid the lack of nonverbal communication and superficial insights, the interview guide consisted of fewer than 15 open-ended questions, as recommended by Boyce & Neale (2006). Questions were written using interview guides by Canfield & Chatelain (2024) and Enger & Gulbrandsen (2020) as references. Interviews began

with background questions before exploring stakeholder views on diversity, its role in event success, and recommendations for SCTT26. Two versions of the guide were created: one for ECS in English, one for ECoC in French, as interviewees from Esch preferred to be interviewed in their native language. The full interview guide can be found in Supplementary Materials and remained flexible based on interviewees' responses. The interview guide was pilot-tested with six volunteers.

Due to geographical spread, only two interviews were conducted in person, while the remaining ten interviews were conducted online. All interviews were audio-recorded with consent for the accuracy of transcriptions. Once transcribed, the audios were permanently deleted to ensure confidentiality. For the transcription of interviews, Good Tape (GDPR-compliant) was used. The transcripts of all 12 interviews were manually checked and cleaned. For both interviews conducted in French (S6, S7), interviews were translated to English manually and checked with a native-french volunteer to ensure accuracy and intended meaning. Interviews were analysed using Atlas.ti to identify a coherent set of key themes within the set of interviews (Besley et al., 2016; Enger & Gulbrandsen, 2020; Guest et al., 2012).

Interview transcripts were analysed using thematic analysis, a flexible qualitative method used to identify, analyse, and report patterns within data. Thematic analysis allowed for detailed interpretations grounded in the participants' experiences while also being theoretically flexible (Braun & Clarke, 2006). This approach was chosen to enable an in-depth understanding of stakeholder perspectives on cross-fertilisation and community-building.

An inductive coding strategy was used, allowing themes to emerge directly from the data. The analysis followed Braun and Clarke's six-phase process: familiarisation with the data, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes, and producing the report. Coding was conducted in [Atlas.ti](#), and an initial codebook was developed and tested on a small sample of interviews. A second coder reviewed this subset to assess the intercoder reliability (ICR), and the codebook was adjusted (O'Connor & Joffe, 2020). The full codebook can be found in the Supplementary Materials. A first round of ICR was performed, but only reached 40.4%. After consulting with the second coder and refining the codebook (e.g. clarifying definitions, merging similar codes), a second round of ICR was performed and reached 85.2%. After this second round, a total of 16.7% of the data was coded by the second coder (2 interviews, randomly picked using a random number generator).

h. Ethics

This research complies with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Ethical approval was obtained from the umbrella approval for the Science Communication and Society department (Leiden University) before conducting the study. Before each interview, participants were sent an informed consent form, outlining research

topics, objectives, data handling procedures, and their right to withdraw at any time. Informed consent was obtained via email using the official template provided by Leiden University (Supplementary materials). All interviews were audio-recorded with participants' permission. Recordings were transcribed and then permanently deleted to ensure data confidentiality. Interview data were pseudonymised with each participant assigned a unique code to protect their identity. No personally identifiable information was included in the analysis or reporting. The identities of each participant were stored securely and only accessible to supervisors.

3. Results

3.1. Case studies

a. Stakeholder diversity and composition

Based on the document analysis, Fisher's test indicated no significant difference in internal vs. external stakeholder distributions for Manchester ($p=0.11$), whereas Leiden and Katowice revealed significant differences across stakeholder categories. The Poisson regression on stakeholder counts found Academia significantly overrepresented across all cities. In Manchester, other stakeholder categories did not differ significantly from Academia (Figure 1).

In Leiden (Figure 2), Academia was the most represented stakeholder group, significantly higher than all other categories (104 external vs. 122 internal stakeholders), followed by Artist and Association/Organisation. Categories like Advocate/Activist, Foundation, Funding, Healthcare, Media, and Student had lower counts ($n=1-12$ stakeholders in these categories) while Company, Cultural place, and Government showed moderate counts ($n=19-28$ stakeholders).

In Katowice (Figure 3), Academia dominated internal stakeholders ($n=1307$ vs. 328 external stakeholders). Artist and Association/Organisation also showed internal prevalence. Conversely, categories such as Advocate/Activist and Government displayed more balanced or externally skewed distributions. Funding was unrepresented ($n=0$). Across Katowice, internal stakeholders consistently outnumbered external ones.

Figure 1. Distribution of stakeholders among categories with external/internal division for ECS16 (Manchester), based on the document analysis. Letters indicate statistically significant groupings based on post hoc comparisons: categories sharing the same letter do not differ significantly, while categories with different letters are significantly different from each other ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 2. Distribution of stakeholders among categories with external/internal division for ECS22 (Leiden), based on the document analysis. Letters indicate statistically significant groupings based on post hoc comparisons: categories sharing the same letter do not differ significantly, while categories with different letters are significantly different from each other ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 3. Distribution of stakeholders among categories with external/internal division for ECS24 (Katowice), based on the document analysis. Letters indicate statistically significant groupings based on post hoc comparisons: categories sharing the same letter do not differ significantly, while categories with different letters are significantly different from each other ($p < 0.05$).

A comparative analysis of Shannon's diversity index (H) and Evenness (E) across Manchester, Leiden, and Katowice revealed distinct patterns in stakeholder diversity and distribution (Table 4). Leiden exhibited the highest internal ($H = 1.87$; $E = 0.14$) and external ($H = 1.90$; $E = 0.15$) relative diversity and evenness. Katowice, while demonstrating moderate external diversity ($H = 1.79$; $E = 0.14$), exhibited the lowest relative internal diversity ($H = 1.23$; $E = 0.09$), indicating a disparity between internal and external stakeholder groups. Manchester ranked between the two in internal diversity ($H = 1.55$; $E = 0.12$) but had the lowest external values ($H = 1.24$; $E = 0.10$), suggesting a more limited external composition.

Table 4. Shannon's index and corresponding evenness for each ECS edition, both in internal and external stakeholders.

City	Internal or External	Shannon's Diversity Index (H)	Evenness (E)
Manchester (ECS16)	External	1.24	0.10
	Internal	1.55	0.12
Leiden (ECS22)	External	1.90	0.15
	Internal	1.87	0.14
Katowice (ECS24)	External	1.79	0.14
	Internal	1.23	0.09

b. Patterns of collaboration

In Manchester, cross-sector collaboration was limited to Academia. Both Leiden and Katowice involved more stakeholder types in collaborations, with Academia central in both.

For Leiden, external stakeholders formed a more complex network, with greater interconnectivity between stakeholders, especially from academia, cultural places, artists, and associations.

Conversely, in Katowice, the network of external stakeholders was simpler, with academia and government at its core. Internal stakeholders in Katowice, however, exhibited a more complex network, with academia being at the centre of most collaborations, and cultural stakeholders being less central than in Leiden (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Network analysis of collaboration in ECS22 (Leiden) and ECS24 (Katowice) with internal and external divisions. Each dot represents a stakeholder category with its respective title. The font size of the stakeholders' categories is proportional to the number of collaborations they appear in. The thickness and colour intensity of the lines are proportional to the amount of collaboration between the stakeholder categories they link.

c. Spatial distribution of activities

A spatial analysis of event distribution against income levels showed a tendency across all three cities for activities to be centred in higher-income areas. In Manchester (median household income €32,196 in 2016, Office for National Statistics UK), a larger portion of events took place in areas with median incomes exceeding €42,800 (Figure 5). Similarly, in Leiden (median household income €31,600 in 2022, Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek), most events occurred in neighbourhoods with income levels ranging between €33,000 and €38,000 (Figure 6). In Katowice (median household income €18,492 in 2024 Główny Urząd

Statystyczny), most events took place in areas with incomes around €16,704–€19,488, encompassing the median (Figure 7).

For all three cities, academic buildings were central to activity-dense areas; however, a majority of events were spread above the campuses.

Figure 5. Spatial distribution of ECS16 activity hotspots overlaid on top of the net household income map (in € thousands per year) in the Greater Manchester region. Darker red areas indicate higher income brackets, while lighter yellow areas represent lower income brackets. The university icon represents the main campus of the University of Manchester.

Figure 6. Spatial distribution of ECS22 activity hotspots overlaid on top of the net household income map (in € thousands per year) in the Leiden region. Darker red areas indicate lower income brackets, while blue areas represent higher income brackets. The university icons represent the two main campuses of the University of Leiden.

Figure 7. Spatial distribution of ECS24 activity hotspots overlaid on top of the net household income map (in € thousands per year) in the Katowice region. Darker red areas indicate higher income brackets, while lighter orange areas represent lower income brackets. The

university icons represent the locations of the University of Silesia and the University of Gliwice.

d. Thematic focus of events

A Fisher's exact test indicated a significant difference in the distribution of activity themes across the three ECS editions ($p = 0.00303$). Subsequent per-theme analysis revealed that Cultural diversity themes ($p = 0.0003$) and Language themes ($p = 0.031$) primarily drove these differences, while other themes showed no significant variation. ECS16 activities predominantly included historical topics (e.g. graphene discovery, industrialisation) and gender diversity (e.g. Women In Science), with limited coverage of other themes. ECS22 had a strong focus on cultural diversity (13%), especially Indonesian and Surinamese culture, followed by the city's history (e.g. microscope discovery, textile industry). Katowice (ECS24) had fewer inclusivity-related events overall, with its highest proportion (7%) for history-centred activities (e.g. mining industry, organ-making). Uniquely, Katowice proposed activities heavily centred around the local language (in this case, Polish), a theme absent in the other two editions (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Percentage distribution of ECS activities across seven inclusion and relevance themes, by city. Percentages reflect how frequently each theme was used among the activities that were coded with at least one of the seven selected themes. Themes represented in Manchester, Leiden, and Katowice are respectively represented in red, green, and blue. Letters above each theme indicate significance in differences of activity distribution across cities based on Fisher's exact test (a: significant difference, b: no significant difference).

3.2. Semi-structured interviews

a. Stakeholder diversity and cross-fertilisation approaches

Stakeholder diversity and cross-fertilisation approaches varied greatly across countries and cultural/social contexts. Diverse stakeholder groups prompted a

shift towards bottom-up and neighbourhood-driven programming, particularly in ECS16 and ECS22. Projects increasingly adopted small-scale, distributed events (6/12 of total respondents) and informal formats that allowed for flexible, responsive, and community-embedded collaboration. One of the stakeholders exemplified:

We deliberately chose small-scale distribution over large-scale centralisation. What often happens with this kind of festive occasion is that there is one big festival, where people can come, but the people who will come to the festival are mainly highly educated, already in the bubble, white, male, etc. Or elderly people who are more interested in science overall, I think. So by making it small and distributed and experimental, I think we opened up many, many new encounters and possibilities to engage (S1).

In Leiden, 4 out of 5 stakeholders emphasised adaptation to community-driven projects, including the “day owner” model, where societal actors could also lead events: “Most of those days had a day owner from a societal role, not from an academic role. That was the strength” (S8). One ECS22 initiative, Quantum Day, illustrates this intersection: linking the university’s quantum research to Ehrenfest’s neighbourhood fostered community-science ties.

Similarly, in Manchester, collaborations with youth, cultural institutions, and businesses (e.g., The Great Science Share, Business of Science Conference) reinforced cross-sector impact. (Appendix 3, Quote 1). Overall, the interviewee viewed ECS16 as a productive environment for establishing long-term connections (Appendix 3, Quote 2)

In contrast, Katowice followed a more structured, academic-led approach (Academic dominance in cross-fertilisation coded across 4/4 of Katowice’s interviews, none in other cities), with limited community co-creation: “We didn’t involve citizens in choosing topics, it was the organisers. We contacted universities a year in advance [...] then built the weekly themes based on what was available” (S5).

While efforts were made to host events outside university buildings to increase accessibility (e.g., parks, libraries, cinemas), the approach lacked the community ownership and informal formats seen in Leiden and Manchester.

Beyond the ECS context, Esch2022 (as an ECoC) showcased a different model rooted in artistic and civic partnerships with strong cross-border collaboration. Its programming focused on small-scale, experiential formats that invited public participation and creative engagement through a nationwide call for projects (2 out of respondents).

Though co-creation was not explicitly mentioned, Esch emphasised interdisciplinarity and audience engagement through playful formats that connected artistic expression to local and regional identities and concerns (1 out of 2 respondents).

b. Strategic planning of stakeholder diversity

Cities varied in how diversity was planned versus emerging “organically”. Katowice used a "checklist" to ensure diversity in audiences, programming, and partnerships. As put out by one of Katowice's directors:

There was a set of rules that we had to engage all the participants, like the families, the small children, the schools, PhD students and also the businesses in every week. [...] So yes, it was mandatory to create a collaboration outside our region and outside Poland, so at the European level (S12).

In Esch, diversity was seen both as an organic outcome of open calls (director) and as strategically planned in programming (project manager) (Appendix 3, Quotes 3-4).

In Manchester, strategic diversity planning was largely carried out through a steering group model, which brought together city-region stakeholders early in the planning phase. This helped embed diversity across the programme, particularly in initiatives like the Science in the City festival:

It was [directly encouraged during the planning]. And again, I think this steering group was a very important part of that. [...] So I think that there were, there were requisite key sort of city stakeholders that were part of this group (S9).

In contrast, 4 out of 5 of Leiden's respondents emphasised that diversity was not mandated by formal institutions, but emerged through the personal commitment of core team members. Several stakeholders pointed to the organic integration of diversity in practice, reflected in the composition of teams and the inclusiveness of programming.

[The director] did a great job inviting all kinds of people. For me, it's not unusual, but I was in the middle of only female people around me. Almost the whole team were female. And all kinds of people. Refugees and other categories. And people who didn't want to be in a category, especially (S2).

c. Challenges in integrating diverse cultural backgrounds and sectors

Across the four cities, integrating diverse cultural backgrounds and sectors brought a range of challenges, primarily institutional inertia, governance tensions, and difficulties in stakeholder outreach. Interviewees also shared valuable insights into how these obstacles were navigated.

Leiden and Katowice both faced resistance rooted in traditional academic and cultural institutions, though this resistance took different forms. In Leiden, 4 out of 5 participants described push-back from academic sectors that upheld hierarchical, top-down decision-making. For example, efforts to move traditional museum activities out into neighbourhoods were resisted by museums, preferring to stay in their own venues, limiting community reach (Appendix 3, Quote 5).

Similarly, Katowice struggled with initial academic rigidity, with faculties submitting rigid, pre-planned programmes that left little room for collaboration (Appendix*, Quote 6). Stereotypical views of interdisciplinarity, reducing the arts to an embellishment rather than an equal partner, further illustrated institutional barriers: “We talked to the Technical University [...] and they said ‘we’re going to invite the Academy of Fine Arts to paint a picture’” (S5).

To overcome this institutional inertia, respondents emphasised the importance of informal networks and personal commitment. Several stakeholders from Leiden and Katowice pointed to the cultural sector’s expertise in participatory approaches as a crucial resource (Appendix 3, Quote 7-8).

Stakeholders from all cities identified significant tensions around governance, coordination, and differing sectoral values. Disparities between institutional protocols and community practices, and contrasting definitions of success, led to frustrations and unmet expectations (5 out of 12 respondents). For example, institutions (universities for ECS, museums for ECoC) viewed success in terms of attendance numbers, while oftentimes the interviewed stakeholders tended to prioritise local relevance and subjective success (Appendix 3, Quote 9).

Esch and Manchester, while experiencing fewer internal institutional barriers, faced challenges related to cross-border and interdisciplinary governance and coordination across multiple organisations. Esch navigated cultural differences and varying success criteria through dialogue and adaptive management: “We are always playing at different levels with different understandings of success. [...] Listening for this kind of project is absolutely essential [...] we need to adapt it to reality” (S6).

Manchester’s main difficulties were logistical and temporal, where the timescale could have potentially hindered the facility of putting together collaborations (Appendix 3, Quote 10).

Engaging diverse external stakeholders, especially businesses, presented notable hurdles in Katowice. Katowice particularly struggled to connect with large companies and media, encountering unresponsiveness to initial contact attempts (3 out of 4 respondents) (Appendix 3, Quote 11).

To overcome this, they adapted their communication strategy to fit local cultural norms, establishing contact through hierarchical channels (Appendix 3, Quote 12):

We decided that we should send emails from our rector of the university because in Poland, in general, there's a hierarchy [...] if it's the rector of the university, it's not good when someone is not replying to him (S10).

d. Diversity and sustainability of community-building initiatives

Stakeholder diversity was seen as essential for an inclusive impact of the ECS title year. Across all four cities, stakeholder diversity was strongly linked to more responsive community engagement and the potential for longer-term impact. However, the depth and sustainability of these benefits depended on factors such as local ownership, institutional flexibility, and ongoing support.

In Leiden, stakeholder diversity was widely seen as essential to context-sensitive community-building. All ECS22 interviewees noted that diverse teams helped adapt content and formats to local needs, improved communication, and built longer-term relationships beyond the project itself:

My interns came from different cultural backgrounds, which really helped sometimes at certain events. [...] It really helped that my two interns were from a different background so people came up to them a little bit more than the white science guys, for example (S3).

In Katowice, while still assessing the impact of ECS24, there were promising signs that diverse stakeholder involvement helped improve accessibility and reshape public perceptions of science, particularly through business involvement:

When there was a company near it, I think that people were thinking that it would be more open for them. That the scientist with the business, the cooperation is good, so it was much better for the recipients (S10).

Manchester, as the earliest case (ECS16), offered more mature evidence of legacy. One stakeholder reflected that bringing together diverse partners helped build lasting relationships and regional confidence: "The legacy continues because many of those people remain in Manchester [...] There is a history now of having worked together" (S9).

Esch also showed how diverse and cross-sectoral collaborations could succeed when supported by thoughtful curation and accessible presentation. For example, combining disciplines helped broaden audience appeal (Appendix 3, Quote 13).

Across cities, outreach to underserved or isolated groups remained a persistent challenge. While efforts were made (e.g. paying attention to the organisational team diversity, collaborating with underserved neighbourhoods, and targeting specific age groups) and cross-fertilisation eased the outreach to communities, several stakeholders acknowledged their limitations (6 out of 12):

“Answer remains, not enough, but we've tried. [...] I'm not sure we could have deep-dived more, getting even more closer than we already did” (S2).

In Esch, stakeholders described difficulties in making some artistic practices accessible or ‘readable’ to the wider public, particularly when art forms were unfamiliar. This shortcoming in terms of readability could have hindered public accessibility to such events. (Appendix 3, Quote 14)

Nine out of twelve interviewees across the four cities reported challenges in evaluating impact and inclusivity due to time, budget, and misaligned evaluation tools. In Leiden, standard surveys failed to capture less formally educated or non-Dutch-speaking residents, and relying on written information was seen as a limitation. (Appendix 3, Quote 15).

ECS stakeholders highlighted the need for clearer evaluation frameworks, as the Manchester stakeholder emphasises: “One of the things that’s lacking with a lot of these events is a clear framework for evaluating these things” (S9).

In Esch, the tight project timelines and lack of sustained financial support were seen as major obstacles to building lasting legacies. Indeed, political turnover and lower funding after the title year made it difficult to sustain the legacy of such collaborations and events. (Appendix 3, Quote 16).

4. Discussion

Stakeholder diversity had been previously linked to significant impacts on innovation and science. Dong et al. (2018) showed that small and diverse teams are more likely to produce leading innovations than relatively larger but less diverse collaborations. These insights are highly relevant to science communication, particularly in informal, large-scale formats like the European Cities of Science.

The comparative analysis of Shannon’s diversity index (H) and Evenness (E) across all three studied ECS revealed structural patterns in how stakeholder diversity was distributed and integrated within these initiatives.

Leiden exhibited the highest relative levels of both internal and external diversity (H=1.865 and H=1.898, respectively), with similar evenness internally and externally. This suggests that Leiden embedded diversity not only in its public-facing events but also within its internal governance and organisational structures. Interestingly, high diversity levels did not seem to arise from any formal policy, but rather from the personal initiatives of Leiden’s directors and interviewed organisers. This suggests that, in the absence of formal diversity frameworks, individual leadership can play an important role in advancing inclusive practices. Such findings are consistent with research highlighting the importance of individual leadership in shaping diversity outcomes through advocacy and stakeholder empowerment (Dwivedi et al., 2024). Moreover, we hypothesise that the case of Esch aligns the closest with Leiden, as

mentions of cross-sector but also cross-border collaborations were strong. Additionally, its open-call model could confirm this hypothesis. Open calls and curated programming approaches likely worked in tandem, with open calls enabling broad participation, while curated events ensured diversity in key outputs.

In Leiden, case studies and interviews both confirmed rather high stakeholder diversity, though academic dominance persisted. Associations/organisations were more represented in this edition than in Manchester and Katowice, likely reflecting co-creation, notably with neighbourhood associations, as co-owners of some ECS events. The presence of associations has been claimed to work as an efficient bridge between institutions and the local public, acting as a “local and familiar anchor” in the neighbourhoods. We hypothesise that these neighbourhood associations functioned as “boundary organisations”, acting as a buffer between academic networks and the public (Hoppe et al., 2013), helping to build trust and more durable community relationships by acting as partners rather than mere participants.

For Katowice, interviewees all mentioned the use of a checklist for cross-sector collaborations, but still widely embedded academically. Katowice presents the particular context of an Eastern European country. As demonstrated by Woldu & Biederman (1999), Polish workers showed the strongest hierarchical behaviour, compared to Russian and American respondents. Such cultural structure could explain the large academic dominance for that specific edition, with only rectors of universities and academies forming the title year consortium (Uniwersytet Śląski w Katowicach, 2024).

Mismatches between case study results and interviews in Manchester likely stem from limited online information, nine years after the title year. Indeed, only a few activities were presented with their matching stakeholders, and few reports were still available. Additionally, only one stakeholder from Manchester could be interviewed, introducing potential bias. Moreover, ECS editions before 2022 were based on a different model than for Leiden and Katowice, with a focus on the ESOF conference, inviting scientists to discuss scientific topics in a traditional conference style. This may explain the strong academic presence and limited external stakeholder diversity. Lastly, the shorter timespan of the Manchester edition, as well as the different engagement model, may explain the lower counts of stakeholders and simpler collaboration networks.

Furthermore, the network analysis revealed that both Leiden and Katowice involved academic institutions centrally in collaborations. Leiden’s network was more distributed, especially externally, displaying strong collaboration between academia and association/organisation, artists, companies and the healthcare domain. In contrast, both of Katowice’s networks were simpler, highlighting a leading presence of academia as the main stakeholder, mainly in collaboration with the government.

This suggests that while both cities maintained academic leadership, Leiden's broader inclusion of diverse stakeholders appeared to support more dynamic cross-fertilisation and stronger local relevance. The more limited role of cultural and civic actors in Katowice pointed to a more formal and institutionally bounded approach, potentially limiting innovation and the ability to respond to community needs. These findings align with qualitative insights indicating that bottom-up engagement and informal partnerships, more prevalent in Leiden, were key to fostering inclusive community-building and trust.

Framed through the "quadruple helix model", Leiden's network reflects a more collaborative ecosystem, where academia, government, civil society, and cultural sectors co-produce knowledge and engagement formats (Carayannis & Campbell, 2010). While Esch did not explicitly focus on science communication, it showcased how small-scale, interdisciplinary formats and cross-border artistic collaborations can foster inclusivity and local relevance. This approach aligns with the "quadruple helix" model in spirit, even if not in formal structure, suggesting alternative routes for co-creation in large-scale public engagement events.

Katowice's collaboration pattern aligned more with the "triple helix model", where academia, government and businesses form the dominant axis, with limited involvement from other stakeholder categories (Leydesdorff & Etzkowitz, 1998). This more hierarchical and centralised model may limit both innovation and inclusivity. These findings reinforce the value of quadruple or even quintuple helix approaches in science communication when aiming to foster inclusive, impactful engagement (Magalhães et al., 2021).

Involving multiple domains in individual events during ECS, especially the arts, can enhance engagement by focusing on the affective domain of learning rather than on the cognitive domain (Friedman, 2013) and by presenting science in engaging, creative ways (Schwartz, 2014). The rise of STEAM (integrating arts into traditional STEM fields) how important creativity and fresh perspectives have become in these fields (de la Garza & Travis, 2019). As such, all studied ECS and ECoC editions included art-science collaborations, with ECS16 and ECS22 engaging external artists, while ECS24 integrated them institutionally through the Academy of Arts. This likely facilitated closer alignment but also raised the potential for disciplinary siloing. Such cross-sector work can lead to misaligned expectations and values, a finding that was also clearly observed during interviews. One potential solution is to have mediators who can bridge multiple social groups and facilitate mutual understanding (Kirby, 2008).

Matias et al. (2021) found that art-science activities co-designed with underserved communities foster stronger engagement and can build longer-term interest in science. When event topics were developed in consultation with the audience, participants better related the content to personal issues. The study also emphasised trust between scientists and communities as key to long-term inclusion, an insight

echoed by half of the stakeholders who highlighted the value of partnering with local groups to build lasting relationships.

Katowice acknowledged the use of a checklist that had to be applied for each of its activities. The checklist was used to ensure that stakeholder collaboration was present in the making of an event, that events also happened outside of academic space, and that events were targeted to a variety of audiences. Despite the use of such a “diversity checklist”, collaboration networks, both internally and externally, were not as complex as expected. Academia was still central and dominant in collaborations during Katowice’s title year, a finding confirmed by the city’s stakeholders during interviews. Such findings could be correlated with research from Koskinen (2022), which shows that institutional solutions are often not enough to increase diversity in science (both at the stakeholder and audience level).

Koskinen proposes, along with research by Ivani and Dutilh Novaes (2022), that personal stakeholder activism may help with pushing diversity in their own organisational team and audience outreach. Such activism can overcome the issue of engaging stakeholders who generally distrust scientists. (Koskinen & Rolin, 2019). As mentioned by a majority of Leiden’s stakeholders in interviews, personal initiative of including diverse groups and trying out new reach-out approaches does seemingly lead to more complex and intertwined collaboration networks.

In Esch, diversity was said to be partially the result of open structural invitations through project calls, rather than institutional mandates. This approach potentially enabled a wider diversity of contributors, though it still required thoughtful curation to ensure representation (European Commission, 2022, p.12).

While all three ECS cities demonstrate some level of stakeholder diversity, especially in outward-facing programming, internal governance structures are still dominated by academic institutions. As multi-stakeholder platform literature has emphasised, stakeholder presence does not automatically translate to influence or power-sharing (Woodhill & van Vugt, 2011; Warner, 2007). Without active facilitation, trust-building, and mechanisms to surface and address power asymmetries, collaborative platforms risk becoming extractive or performative. This may explain why internal stakeholder diversity remains low and why strategic decisions often reflect the norms and interests of the academic conveners (Brouwer et al., 2013).

Due to differences in ECS models, Manchester featured fewer, less geographically distributed events around the Greater Manchester area. Indeed, the shorter time span of Manchester and its bigger focus on the ESOF conference (also financially) led to a smaller event distribution.

Manchester and Leiden both presented an event distribution more focused on higher-income areas. This could indicate a potential socio-economic bias in planning. As mentioned by a project manager from Leiden, bringing events to local marketplaces in neighbourhoods became only more prominent for themselves over the year: “So I noticed that throughout the year, I was more and more focused on

going to markets. Just getting a stand there” (S4). Bringing those science events where the people are usually only seems to have become more regular practice as the year went by, potentially revealing that such outreach was not present in the initial planning.

Katowice displayed a more balanced distribution, with events even extending outside of the main city and throughout the whole Silesian region. As opposed to Manchester and Leiden, Katowice’s stakeholder explicitly mentioned the use of a checklist to ensure events happen across the region, in “everyday spaces”. Therefore, in the case of Katowice, event distribution was strategically planned from the beginning, leading to a fairer distribution across neighbourhoods. This aligns with research from Du et al. (2024), which underlines the importance of strategic plans and intentional outreach to ensure equitable public engagement.

The thematic focus of activities related to community and inclusivity reflected distinct local identities and priorities. In Manchester, emphasis on historical themes (e.g. industrial revolution, graphene discovery), alongside gender diversity topics, pointed to a targeted emphasis on scientific heritage and gender inclusivity. The limited thematic scope would have likely been shaped by the shorter timespan. These findings may also align with the narrower stakeholder representation. This echoes findings by García & Cox (2013), who noted that cities with narrower thematic agendas often point to a smaller or less diverse group of people involved in planning, reducing wider community resonance with the events.

In contrast, Leiden’s ECS22 programme demonstrated a broader inclusivity approach, with 13% of activities highlighting cultural diversity, particularly around Indonesia and Suriname, reflecting postcolonial engagement. This aligned with national conversations and, as Lähdesmäki et al. (2020) argue, enhances the legitimacy and social impact of cultural events through responsive stakeholder collaboration.

In Katowice’s ECS24, history-themed activities were the most frequent category, but the overall representation of the inclusivity topics was lower compared to the two other editions. A unique aspect of Katowice was the presence of Polish language-focused activities, a theme absent in the other cities, suggesting a more inward-facing approach to community-building, emphasising national and linguistic cohesion rather than intercultural outreach. While this may resonate with local audiences, it may also indicate a less diverse stakeholder base or limited cross-sector integration. As noted by Ozdemir et al. (2023), diversity in stakeholder backgrounds is strongly linked to increased creativity and broader problem-solving potential, suggesting that the thematic limitations in Katowice may have stemmed in part from a narrower planning coalition. These differences in themes are backed up by our statistical analysis, which showed that cultural diversity and language were the key themes driving the overall differences between the cities. This highlights how each city’s unique identity and stakeholder priorities shape the focus of its inclusivity efforts.

Overall, each city's thematic design reflected its local historical, demographic, and political context.

For a majority of interviewees across all three ECS, a main challenge was related to a lack of a framework to measure impact and inclusive outreach at the end of the title year. Indeed, no general guidelines seemingly existed for ECS to measure success, impact, or legacy. As this is a challenge that was less strictly mentioned by ECoC stakeholders, we suggest that the European Commission leads the writing of "*Guidelines for the cities' own evaluations of the results of their SCTT*", such as it exists for ECoC (European Commission, 2018). In line with a recommendation from Manchester's stakeholders, we also recommend that the European Commission proposes a formal evaluation framework for all involved SCTT cities, which would help comparative analysis across cities and potentially form practice-based suggestions for future editions.

Limitations and recommendations for future research

This study highlights the value of stakeholder diversity in fostering cross-fertilisation and community-building in European science initiatives, but has some limitations. Due to time constraints, Esch2022 (ECoC) could not be analysed via stakeholder mapping, network analysis, or spatial thematic assessments, limiting direct comparisons with ECS cases. Additionally, the lack of responses from potential interviewees limited the inclusion of other ECoCs, particularly from Eastern and Southern Europe. Future research should address this gap for broader representation.

Additionally, impact reports from Manchester (ECS16) were not available publicly online, while Katowice's (ECS24) reports had not yet been published at the time of this research. This limited a comparative analysis of legacy and impact across the cases. We recommend that future research gather and analyse complete impact and legacy reports across cases to better understand the sustained effects of stakeholder diversity and community-building efforts.

Only 12 interviews were conducted in this study (10 ECS, 2 ECoC), with underrepresentation of ECS16 (n=1), limiting the generalisation of results. A more balanced sample would improve robustness and help reach data saturation across all studied cities.

Lastly, snowball sampling may have introduced bias, as interviewees might have recommended peers with strong Diversity, Equity, and Inclusivity interests, potentially leading to an overrepresentation of positive or supportive views. For future studies, we would recommend selecting stakeholders from different institutional backgrounds (e.g. via stratified sampling) to avoid this bias.

As a next step, future research could explore longer-term perceptions of large-scale science communication initiatives among citizens. Indeed, comparing these with the views of stakeholders involved in ECS would offer valuable insight into how public engagement outcomes align.

Moreover, the same process could be done to evaluate the long-term legacy for involved stakeholders. Such research could focus on observing potential lasting collaborations, projects or articles that emerged from the ECS year.

5. Recommendations

a) Recommendations for SCTT26 stakeholders

Insights from ECS and ECoC stakeholders offered practice-based recommendations for future SCTT stakeholders, particularly regarding cross-fertilisation, inclusivity and community-driven engagement.

A central theme across interviews was flexibility and “productive messiness”. Rather than adhering to rigid plans and sticking to them, one stakeholder from ECS22 emphasised non-linear processes shaped by curiosity, feedback, and experimentation throughout the title year. Such openness was believed to foster creativity and lead to deeper, more authentic community engagement.

Participatory approaches were widely encouraged. Instead of top-down dissemination, three stakeholders recommended participatory approaches that empower citizens to co-create and co-own events. This includes integrating with local events and institutions, using informal and accessible venues where citizens are regularly present (e.g., markets, libraries) and starting with the interests or concerns of communities rather than institutional agendas.

Inclusivity was often framed as “talentship”, recognising and nurturing the unique talents and knowledge of individuals regardless of their backgrounds. Building trust-based, long-term partnerships with early community involvement was seen as important to maintaining engagement and relevance. Success, according to many stakeholders, should be measured not by attendance but by sparking even a single moment of meaningful connection.

Interviewees also highlighted the need for a balanced project design. Combining creative freedom with shared frameworks, clear planning, adequate funding, and open dialogue to align expectations across stakeholders is necessary to ensure lasting impact.

Legacy planning emerged as a recommendation from both ECoC stakeholders. Sustained partnerships, institutional memory, and long-term structures should be considered from the beginning, ideally by leveraging existing networks and experienced practitioners.

In hierarchical contexts, engagement with non-institutional businesses should ideally be initiated by high-level institutional representatives (e.g. university rectors).

Communications with non-institutional businesses should emphasise mutual value and shared goals rather than financial needs, positioning partnerships as opportunities for societal impact and innovation.

There was a call for academic engagement as a professional duty. Universities should act as active community partners (e.g. via Open University models, intergenerational programs, and public science events), and institutional structures should support these efforts, even without external partners.

Lastly, for future SCTT initiatives, universities must be equal partners in both planning and delivery. Grant structures should reflect this shared responsibility to avoid overly promotional events and maintain scientific relevance. This balance was believed by the stakeholders to support interdisciplinarity, inclusivity, and stronger ties between communities and academia.

b) Recommendation for the European Commission as a funding agency

While questioning interviewees about possible recommendations for the future SCTT initiative stakeholders, all interviewees had recommendations for the European Commission as a funding agency.

A main concern was short-term funding, which hampered long-term impact. We recommend allocating part of the funding beyond that year to help cities sustain newly created collaborations.

Additionally, a majority of interviewees acknowledged measuring inclusion as another main challenge. One interviewee suggested the creation of a constant framework to measure inclusion across SCTT each year. This would ultimately help each city assess its outreach at the end of the title year, but also enable comparative learning.

Lastly, many stakeholders expressed willingness to share their expertise. Thus, we suggest forming a panel of stakeholders who participated in such mega-events to guide and support future SCTT stakeholders. This panel should aim to adapt to the creative freedom of these new stakeholders while providing experience-based suggestions.

6. Conclusion

This study set out to explore what SCTT26 can learn from how stakeholder diversity influenced interdisciplinary collaboration and community-building in previous ECS and ECoC. Through a comparative analysis of ECS16 (Manchester), ECS22 (Leiden), and ECS24 (Katowice), stakeholder diversity appeared to play a central

role in shaping inclusiveness, creativity, and sustainability of large-scale science communication initiatives.

Stakeholder diversity significantly shaped cross-fertilisation approaches by enabling deeper collaboration across sectors such as academia, government, civil society, and the arts. Leiden's ECS22 exemplifies this, demonstrating a "quadruple helix", reflected in several activities carried out in partnership with local associations. While these collaborations suggest the potential for co-production of knowledge and trust-building with local communities, further insights are needed from the community perspective to confirm the extent of such processes. By contrast, Katowice's ECS24, while formally structured with tools like a diversity checklist, leaned heavily on academic institutions, resulting in more limited external collaboration and a "triple helix" governance structure. This contrast underlines that diversity cannot be achieved through formal tools alone but also requires active personal leadership and informal networks to bring underrepresented voices into the planning process.

Challenges in integrating different sectors included institutional inertia, mismatched expectations, and deeply rooted hierarchical norms, as seen particularly in Katowice. Interviews revealed that informal collaboration and the involvement of boundary-spanning stakeholders (e.g. neighbourhood associations) were essential for translating cross-sector diversity into actual impact.

The extent to which diversity was strategically planned varied across countries. In Leiden, diversity emerged largely from personal commitment rather than institutional mandate, while in Katowice, it was more structurally embedded yet limited in scope. This suggests that while formal strategies are valuable, they must be complemented by a bottom-up culture of inclusion.

Stakeholder diversity also appeared important for long-term sustainability and impact. Although data limitations make it difficult to assess legacy effects comprehensively, interviewees emphasised that relationships built through inclusive, co-created events were more likely to continue after the title year. Diverse stakeholder engagement helped ensure that science communication activities resonated with a wider range of communities, including underserved groups, an essential factor for lasting impact.

From this study, several key lessons emerge for SCTT26, based on ECS and ECoC stakeholders' experiences, which include:

- When contacting potential partners for collaboration, frame your demand by emphasising mutual values, shared goals and benefits for the partner, rather than financial needs.
- Avoiding top-down dissemination models, promoting participatory approaches and co-creation with civil society as much as possible.

- Preparing for legacy in the planning phase and considering the potential long-term impacts from the start.

In conclusion, SCT26 should view stakeholder diversity not as a checkbox, but as a foundational principle for co-creation, innovation, and public outreach. Only through meaningful and sustained inclusion can science communication serve as a true bridge between science and society.

AI disclaimer: Grammarly was used to correct spelling and grammar errors. ChatGPT was used to brainstorm titles and to shorten bits of text, as well as to help with RStudio scripts.

Example scripts: *"I want to compare counts of stakeholder categories between each other. I have 13 categories, each divided into Internal and External. I wanna know whether one (or more) category is more present for each division. I have the count data, and some categories have less than 5 stakeholders. How do I do that in R?"*

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Appendices

Appendix 1. Stakeholder categories.

Stakeholder category	Definition
Academia	Includes professors, researchers involved closely with universities and higher education
Advocates/Activists	Individuals or groups actively working to promote, oppose, or raise awareness about specific causes, policies, or social issues.
Artist	Encompasses people engaged in an activity related to creating art, practising the arts, or demonstrating art.
Association/Organisation	Formal groups or entities formed around shared interests or purposes, often non-profit.
Company	For-profit businesses or enterprises engaged in commercial, industrial, or professional activities.
Cultural places (museums, theatre, cinemas, etc)	Physical venues or institutions that preserve, present, or promote cultural heritage and creative works to the public.
Entrepreneur	Individuals who start and run new businesses or ventures, often characterised by innovation.
Foundation	Non-profit organisations that typically provide funding, support, or advocacy for specific causes or communities, are often established with an endowment.
Government	Includes ministers, municipalities and their representants
Healthcare	Organisations and professionals involved in the provision of medical services, health education, and wellness programs.
Media	Channels and institutions involved in the production and dissemination of information, news, or entertainment, including print, broadcast, and digital platforms.
Students	Individuals currently enrolled in educational institutions
Funding	Entities or individuals that provide financial resources or investment for projects, initiatives, or organizations.

Appendix 2. Content analysis codes of activities.

Code	Description	Examples
History	<p>The activity makes use of local monuments, presents local discoveries, and/or is related to the city's heritage. The code is also applied to activities relating to past events such as war, colonisation, local disasters.</p> <p>Manchester's heritage: industrialisation, graphene</p> <p>Leiden's heritage: textile industry, canals, windmills</p> <p>Katowice's heritage: mining, metal industry, organ-making</p>	<p>Graphene exhibition in Manchester 2016</p> <p>Route of Discoveries in Leiden 2022</p> <p>Life after life of underground mines in Katowice 2024</p>
Culture	<p>The activity focuses on other cultures than the main one of the city. The code is also applied if the activity is focused on other beliefs and/or spirituality. This code also encompasses activities around "general diversity"</p>	<p>Maori day in the Old Observatory in Leiden 2022</p> <p>The cultural heritage of the Moroccan people in Katowice 2024</p>
Age	<p>The activity is mainly discussing topics around either elders or kids. The activity can relate to elder/kid's health, elder/kid lifestyle (nursing homes, daycare, etc)</p>	<p>7th Meeting of the Nursing Home and Long Term Care Research International working group in Leiden 2022</p> <p>Age has many names - a multidimensional conceptualization of the aging process in Katowice 2024</p>
Gender	<p>The activity discusses issues related especially to females or non-binary people.</p>	<p>Women in science in Manchester 2016</p> <p>I am extraorbi+nary in Leiden 2022</p> <p>Discussion panel: Women in the development of artificial intelligence in Katowice 2024</p>
Accessibility	<p>The activity addresses topics regarding neurodivergence and/or disabilities</p>	<p>The Power of ADHD in Leiden 2022</p> <p>Educational workshop on the work of assistance dogs and disabilities workshop in Katowice 2024</p>
Language	<p>The activity is centred around teaching or putting the light on the local language/dialect.</p>	<p>Everyone can be Different – on developing intercultural sensitivity in teaching Polish as a foreign/second language in Katowice 2024</p>
People	<p>The activity is focused on presenting/meeting/discovering with local famous people (scientists, artists, Nobel Prizes, athletes etc).</p>	<p>Unique lecture about Huizinga in Leiden 2022</p> <p>Opening of the exhibition: Maria Skłodowska-Curie. In Love with Science and a meet-the-author session in Katowice 2024</p>

Appendix 3. Quotes

Quote 1: *"...it's designed to bring young people, school children to present science to each other... like a scientific conference for kids."* (S9)

Quote 2: *"That was developed during the festival, so I would say between the arts sector and the science sector in particular, but again, the education sector I think still has a legacy to it, which was which is born partly out of the collaboration between the universities over that period. And I think that was a very productive period for collaboration."* (S9)

Quote 3: *"[The diversity of stakeholders involved and cross-fertilisation] developed organically and projects like Sound of Data were able to take place because we launched a very large call for projects. Where we only set as criteria, in fact, feasibility criteria obviously, but which corresponded to the European context and also to the context of the European Capital of Culture project; of innovation, of sharing, and of accessibility as well."* (S6)

Quote 4: *"Yes. Absolutely. It was something that was very present throughout the entire programming, to varying degrees. This was reflected in works that were produced for the exhibition or at least for Esch 2022. And it was reflected, let's say in a somewhat more distant manner, with the works we presented, which were existing works that were part of the three major exhibitions."* (S7)

Quote 5: *"Step out. And then please, come along, go to the neighbourhoods... Time after time, [a local museum] said 'no, we want to do it in our museum'... They were attracting usual suspects this way."* (S2)

Quote 6: *"It sounds perfect, but it actually isn't... they wanted to do it their way."* (S5)

Quote 7: *"Not from the formal institution, but from the individuals that really got it [...] The cultural sector is really good at [this]; that muscle doesn't exist in our university."* (S8)

Quote 8: *"We started treating it more like a dialogue with people, not with faculties or departments."* (S5)

Quote 9: *"The organiser was disappointed [...] but we were super enthusiastic because it worked."* (S2)

Quote 10: *"It's just making sure you have enough time... that was probably the biggest [challenge]."* (S9)

Quote 11: *"But what was most challenging, it was the contact with big businesses, when we were trying to send emails, or make phone calls and so on without any answers. So I think that this was the most challenging thing."* (S10)

Quote 12: *“I started quite early using the main office of the European City of Science, [...] and the fact that it was not me as a professor, but as the coordinator of European City of Science, of one of the weeks of European City of Science. When I called the radio or sent an e-mail to Polish television, the answer was typically yes: “Yeah, we will do something. We don’t know what day, but we will be with you.” (S11)*

Quote 13: *“It’s because they bridge that gap, but in an extremely natural and very fluid way. Once the dialogue takes place and we have a clear and engaging explanation [...] the audience is there and appreciated the works, right?” (S7)*

Quote 14: *“What was perhaps a little more difficult was the readability of the work from the outside [...] we don’t look at dance in the same way we look at a work of art or a video.” (S7)*

Quote 15: *“We were dependent on a question list [...] in Dutch, for example, not in Arabic or Chinese. [...] So we were relying on written information instead of mouth-to-mouth communication.” (S1)*

Quote 16: *“Political representatives expect radical improvements by the end of the year, but the bulk of work is still to be done afterwards.” (S6)*

Supplementary Materials

Supplementary materials can be found via: [Supplementary materials thesis](#)